

KWAME NKRUMAH UNIVERSITY OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY - KNUST

KUMASI - GHANA

SCHOOL OF GRADUATE STUDIES -IDL

COLLEGE OF ENGINEERING

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**ENHANCING GHANA'S ENERGY SECTOR SUSTAINABILITY THROUGH
MACHINE LEARNING-BASED SOLAR FORECASTING AND DATA-DRIVEN
POLICY INTEGRATION**

BY

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NOVEMBER 2025

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POLICY INTEGRATION**

By

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A Project submitted to the Department of Mechanical Engineering
Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, Kumasi, in
partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of

MASTER OF SCIENCE (ENERGY AND SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT)

Faculty of Mechanical and Chemical Engineering, College of Engineering

DECLARATION

The dissertation “Enhancing Ghana’s energy sector sustainability through machine learning-based solar forecasting and data-driven policy integration” was done entirely under the supervision of **PROF. (MRS.) SYLVANA RUDITH KING**

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DEDICATION

I sincerely dedicate this dissertation to Almighty God and my dearest parents whose support has brought me this far.

To my parents, siblings and to my loved ones and friends who helped make this work a success, you are deeply appreciated.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I am deeply grateful to God for His guidance and grace throughout the journey of this research project. His strength and mercies have been the driving force behind every step and I am truly thankful for that.

My heartfelt appreciation goes to my indefatigable supervisor, Prof. (Mrs.) Sylvana Rudith King, her leadership, resolute dedication and indispensable expertise throughout this research journey. Her insightful feedback and constructive criticism motivated me to strive for excellence and I am truly grateful for her mentorship.

A special thank you goes to my parents and work colleagues for the patience afforded me while going through this research project.

ABSTRACT

Ghana's energy sector remains heavily reliant on thermal and hydroelectric sources, wherein both are susceptible to climate variability and high operational costs. This study enhances the sustainability of Ghana's energy mix through machine learning-based solar forecasting and data-driven policy integration. The study focused on utilizing machine learning models to learn from historical solar irradiance data from 1984 to 2022 for Ghana, with projections extended to 2030. Solar irradiance refers to the amount of solar radiation received per unit area and it is typically measured in watts per square meter (W/m^2). Solar irradiance is critical as it determines the potential power output of solar panels and serves as an input for predicting solar energy availability over different time horizons. The research trained and evaluated three models: Random Forest, XGBoost and Deep Neural Networks for national solar irradiance prediction. XGBoost achieved the highest accuracy with a coefficient of determination of 0.9575 and a Root Mean Square Error of $0.1086 \text{ kWh}/\text{m}^2/\text{day}$ which outperformed the other models. The findings identified the Upper East Region, Upper West Region and Northern Region as high potential solar zones with dry-season months of November to March showing peak irradiance levels exceeding $5.5 \text{ kWh}/\text{m}^2/\text{day}$. The study recommends integrating these forecasts into Ghana's renewable energy policies to guide infrastructure investments while supporting Sustainable Development Goal 7. Despite data resolution and computational limitations, the findings provide an evidence-based framework for advancing clean and resilient energy planning in Ghana.

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ABBREVIATIONS/ACRONYMS

ML - Machine Learning

RMSE - Root Mean Square Error

MAE - Mean Absolute Error

RE - Renewable Energy

DL - Deep Learning

DNN - Deep Neural Network

PV - Photovoltaic

RF - Random Forest

ReLU - Rectilinear Linear Activation

ANN - Artificial Neural Networks

SDG - Sustainable Development Goals

XGBoost - Extreme Gradient Boosting

R^2 - Coefficient of Determination (R-squared)

GHI - Global Horizontal Irradiance

DNI - Direct Normal Irradiance

DHI – Diffuse Horizontal Irradiance

GMet - Ghana Meteorological Agency

IEA - International Energy Agency

IRENA - International Renewable Energy Agency

GBM - Gradient Boosting Machine

SVM - Support Vector Machine

IoT - Internet of Things

CO₂ - Carbon Dioxide

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CHAPTER 1:

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Ghana's growing energy demand over the years has emphasized the need for a sustainable and diversified energy mix. The country relies heavily on thermal sources of energy and hydropower which has hugely been affected by climate change. Climate change has caused significant variability in water levels at major dams in the country impacting the reliability of hydroelectric power (Energy Commission Ghana, 2021).

Thermal energy generation which now constitutes about 70 percent of Ghana's energy mix contributes significantly to environmental pollution. The energy sector in Ghana is currently expensive to operate due to the high contribution of thermal sources of energy and it has saddled the country with debt (Energy Commission Ghana, 2021). This has constrained investment in other sectors mainly affecting education and healthcare sectors in terms of infrastructure and innovation. Consequently, it has become economically burdensome operating Ghana's energy sector and this demands an urgent attention to remediate such (Energy Commission Ghana, 2021).

Ghana has a geographical advantage due to high solar irradiance across various regions offering a viable alternative energy source that is clean, sustainable and cost effective. The average solar irradiance in Ghana ranges from 4.5kWh/m² to 6.0kWh/ m² throughout the year offering immense potential for photovoltaic (PV) adoption and deployment (Quansah et al., 2022). Solar irradiance refers to the measure of solar intensity received from the sun (Sharma and Kakkar, 2018). Utilization of solar energy resource efficiently offers Ghana an avenue to reduce reliance

on costly fuels for thermal power and the pollution associated with thermal energy sources. This enhances sustainability and aids in Ghana's alignment with Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) number seven which emphasizes clean energy.

However, harnessing the full potential of solar energy in Ghana requires accurate solar forecasting tools to inform policymakers and hence optimize deployment. Machine learning (ML) techniques aid in modelling complex nonlinear relationships in data and have promising tools for forecasting solar irradiance and energy output (Sharma and Kakkar, 2018). Analysis of long-term solar irradiation data across all regions in Ghana can help identify the best months and regions for solar investment. The insights can guide national energy strategies which shifts emphasis toward solar energy during months with high solar irradiance and optimization of hydropower utilization during periods with low solar irradiation.

Recent studies by (Asiedu et al., 2024) have applied machine learning methods such as Random Forests and Neural Networks to forecast solar photovoltaic output in Ghana affirming their potential to complement decision-making. This research contributes to evolving literature by developing a countrywide machine learning-based forecasting model that not merely forecasts solar availability but also integrates with policy frameworks for sustainable energy planning (Asiedu et al., 2024).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Ghana's energy mix is constituted hugely by thermal sources of energy and hydropower which is highly susceptible to seasonal variability. The energy sector is vulnerable due to overreliance on thermal sources which is costly and environmentally unfriendly. Despite abundant solar potential, the country lacks a comprehensive data-driven framework to forecast solar irradiance

across all regions and months accurately. Existing forecasting models are localized or lack precision needed for strategic planning in the energy sector.

Moreover, integration of such models into national energy policy remains limited.

Consequently, the energy sector is plagued by financial constraints while thermal power plants continue emitting harmful pollutants into the atmosphere (REN21, 2020). This undermines environmental sustainability. There is a distinctively clear gap in tools that can dynamically identify months with high solar potential across regions. This tool can help guide in allocation of investment and infrastructure effectively. Addressing this gap requires machine learning-based forecasting models tailored to Ghana's climatic and geographic realities.

1.3 Research Questions of the Study

1. How can machine learning techniques enhance the accuracy of forecasting solar energy output across Ghana?
2. Which months and regions have the highest forecasted solar energy potential in Ghana?
3. What are the most effective machine learning models for solar forecasting under the Ghanaian weather conditions?
4. How can solar forecasts be integrated into the national energy policy to optimize renewable energy investment?

1.4 Objectives of the Study

1.4.1 General Objective

The general objective of this research is to enhance the sustainability of Ghana's energy sector through machine learning-based solar irradiance forecasting and informed policy recommendations for renewable energy integration.

1.4.2 Specific Objectives

1. To collect and preprocess solar irradiance data from the NASA POWER dataset to analyze solar patterns across Ghana.
2. To apply machine learning models to predict solar irradiance trends annually.
3. To identify months and regions with highest solar energy potential.
4. To evaluate the performance of different machine learning models in forecasting solar irradiance under Ghanaian climate.
5. To provide policy recommendations for strategic solar investment.

1.5 Justification of the Study

This study addresses a critical gap in Ghana's renewable energy sector planning by providing a model that forecasts solar irradiance across Ghana. Moreover, this study also leverages machine learning techniques to improve forecasting accuracy which is vital for infrastructure planning and energy security.

Furthermore, this study supports policy development by proving evidence-based recommendations on where and when to invest in solar infrastructure. Alignment of solar

investment within months with high solar energy potential and reliance on hydropower during months with low solar potential can help Ghana achieve a more resilient energy mix. In addition, by reducing reliance on thermal power, the country can lower emission of greenhouse gases and advance towards sustainable energy solutions.

1.6 Scope of the Study

The study covers all regions in Ghana. It spans solar irradiance data collected across Ghana from 1984 to 2022 to capture seasonal variations. Technically, this study applies and compares multiple machine learning algorithms such as Random Forests, XGBoost and deep machine learning models.

However, this study does not cover the financial implementation of solar projects or installation logistics.

1.7 Summary of Methodology

The study will begin with collection and aggregation of solar irradiance data from NASA POWER datasets from 1984 to 2022 for Ghana. The data will then undergo cleaning, normalization and handling of missing values. Machine Learning Models such as XGBoost, Random Forest and Deep Neural Networks will be trained on the data and evaluated with metrics such Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Root Mean Square (RMSE) and coefficient of determination to determine forecasting accuracy. The subsequent results will be analyzed to identify the best performing models, regions and months in Ghana with highest solar energy potential.

Consequently, evidence-based energy policy suggestions will be made where feasible to guide sector policy makers and key stakeholders to make informed decisions to improve investment in solar energy.

1.8 Limitations of the Study

1. Availability and completeness of high-resolution irradiance data may affect model accuracy.

Mitigation: To address this, the study applies data imputation techniques for missing values.

2. Computational limitations may restrict the complexity of deep learning models.

Mitigation: The study prioritizes scalable machine learning algorithms and leverages optimized computing resources such cloud infrastructure where feasible.

3. Policy implementation is outside the scope of this study.

Mitigation: While direct implementation is excluded, this study provides evidence-based policy recommendations that can guide policymakers and stakeholders.

1.9 Organization of the Thesis

Chapter One introduces the study and its context

Chapter Two reviews relevant literature on solar energy potential, machine learning forecasting and national energy policy.

Chapter Three presents the research methodology and model design.

Chapter Four discusses the results and interprets the findings.

Chapter Five interprets the findings from the results.

Chapter Six offers' conclusions and policy recommendations.

CHAPTER 2:

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

Global transition toward sustainable energy systems has increased the need for accurate renewable energy forecasting due to its abundance and environmental benefits. In Ghana, integration of renewable energy particularly solar energy into the grid is paramount to reducing heavy reliance on costly thermal energy sources (Energy Commission Ghana, 2021).

Policies to regulate alternation between renewable and non-renewable energy sources to ensure maximum utilization is lacking in the current policy framework of the country. This gap is critical given Ghana's escalating energy demand which has outpaced energy supply. Consequently, frequent power outages and economic losses estimated at 2% to 6% of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) annually have occurred (Energy Commission Ghana, 2021). The absence of robust forecasting tools and policy frameworks hampers the country's ability to leverage solar resources. Hence, this has necessitated the need for advanced methodologies that adopts machine learning to inform strategic decisions in national energy planning. Ghana's solar energy adoption remains

Figure 2.1 Ghana installed solar capacity

Source: IRENA (2023)

2.2 Solar Energy Potential and Challenges

Renewable energy sources comprise geothermal, wind energy, biofuels and others but solar energy particularly remains the cornerstone of renewable energy strategies worldwide due to its sustainability and scalability. Solar photovoltaic (PV) capacity has grown significantly with the International Energy Agency reporting a global installed capacity of over 700 GW (REN21, 2020). This growth reflects a 20% annual increase in solar photovoltaic installations since 2015. It is mainly driven by declining costs of solar panels and supportive policies by countries like China and Germany (World Bank, 2021). The scalability of solar energy is further evidenced by its contribution to 3.7% of global electricity production by 2020 (International Energy Agency, 2020). Solar energy is projected to reach 10% global energy contribution by 2030 under current trends (International Energy Agency, 2020). In Africa, solar potential is immense due to high availability

of sunlight due to the continent's geographical position. There are high levels of solar irradiation averaging 4.5 kWh/m²/day to 6.5 kWh/m²/day across the continent (International Renewable Energy Agency, 2015). Abundant solar energy is particularly pronounced in sub-Saharan Africa where countries like Ghana, Nigeria and Kenya are located. These countries receive consistent solar irradiance making solar energy a viable solution for addressing energy access gaps especially in rural areas where 70% lack access to reliable electricity (International Renewable Energy Agency, 2015). In Ghana, however, (Quansah et al., 2022) found that solar irradiance ranges from 4.5 kWh/m²/day to 6.0 kWh/m²/day, making it a viable alternative to hydropower and thermal energy. This range is particularly pronounced in the Northern, Upper East and Upper West regions where solar irradiance often exceeds 5.5 kWh/m²/day making it ideal for large scale solar farms (Quansah et al., 2022). The study also noted that Ghana's coastal regions, such as Greater Accra, experienced slightly lower irradiance due to cloud cover but nonetheless remains suitable for distributed solar systems.

Figure 2.2 Share of energy mix in Ghana.

Source: IPPAG (2024)

The Figure 2.2 displays Ghana's energy mix distribution according to various energy sources highlighting the disproportionate share of renewables.

However, significant challenges such as variability in solar irradiance due to weather patterns and lack of forecasting tools hinder deployment. In a study in South Africa, (Wright et al. 2018) highlighted that seasonal cloud cover and dust significantly affect solar output necessitating advanced forecasting models. The study emphasized dust accumulation on photovoltaic panels during dry seasons can reduce efficiency by up to 15% (Wright et al. 2018). Furthermore, it was also established in the research that cloud cover in coastal regions like Cape Town further complicated output reliability (Wright et al. 2018). These challenges are exacerbated by lack of localized models tailored to South Africa's diverse microclimates. Similarly, (Asiedu et al., 2024) noted that Ghana's heavy reliance on thermal power which makes up 70% of the energy mix

increases costs and environmental pollution. This emphasizes the need for data-driven solar integration strategies. Consequently, this reliance has led to estimated \$1.5 billion in annual fuel import costs for thermal plants (Energy Commission Ghana, 2021). This contributes to greenhouse gas emissions equivalent to 12 million tons of CO₂ annually undermining Ghana's commitments under the Paris Agreement (Asiedu et al., 2024). The integration of solar energy could reduce these costs by 30% to 40% if supported by accurate forecasting and strategic policy interventions (Adenle, 2020).

2.3 Machine Learning in Solar Forecasting

Machine learning has emerged as a powerful tool for solar irradiance and energy output forecasting due to its ability to model complex and non-linear relationships in data (Sharma and Kakkar, 2018). Machine learning has the capability of modelling complex data and recognizes patterns in data to make accurate predictions. This capability is immensely valuable in handling high-dimensional and complex meteorological datasets, including variables like temperature, cloud cover and wind speed which influence solar irradiance (Voyant *et al.*, 2017).

Figure 2.3 Solar energy annual capacity

Source: TheRoundup (2021)

The Figure 2.3 displays the rising adoption of solar energy over the years and machine learning models can guide predictions for where best to invest in solar energy in Ghana.

Machine learning models excel in capturing temporal and spatial variations making them superior to traditional statistical approaches which often fail to account for non-linear weather dynamics (Voyant *et al.*, 2017).

Studies have demonstrated efficacy of machine learning models such as Random Forests (RF), Support Vector Machines (SVM) and Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) in solar forecasting (Voyant *et al.*, 2017). The study compared multiple machine learning models for solar irradiance prediction in France, finding out Artificial Neural Networks outperformed traditional statistical

methods with a coefficient of determination value of 0.92. The study tested ANN against SVM and RF across 10 French cities, noting that ANN's ability to model complex temporal patterns resulted in a 20% improvement in forecasting accuracy over linear regression models, particularly for short-term predictions (Voyant *et al.*, 2017). The study also highlighted the importance of incorporating satellite-derived cloud data to enhance model performance

In India, (Sharma and Kakkar, 2018) applied Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM) to forecast solar output achieving an impressive Mean Absolute Error (MAE) of 5.2% under diverse climatic conditions. Their model leveraged historical data from 15 meteorological stations across India, demonstrating GBM's robustness in handling seasonal monsoons and high humidity, which are similar to Ghana's tropical climate (Sharma and Kakkar, 2018). The study reported that GBM reduced forecasting errors by 10% compared to SVM under cloudy conditions.

In Africa, machine learning applications are recently gaining traction. A study in Nigeria by (Ozoegwu, Mgbemene and Ozor, 2017) utilized Artificial Neural Networks to predict solar irradiance with a Root Mean Square Error of 3.8% emphasizing suitability for tropical climates. The study used a 10-year dataset from Lagos and Abuja, incorporating variables like solar zenith angle and atmospheric pressure, which improved ANN's predictive power in Nigeria's humid and dusty environments (Ozoegwu, Mgbemene and Ozor, 2017). The model's success in Nigeria suggests its applicability to Ghana given the similar climatic conditions characterized by high humidity and seasonal Harmattan dust.

In Ghana, (Asiedu et al., 2024) employed Random Forests and Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) to forecast photovoltaic output in Kumasi, reporting a coefficient of determination with value of 0.89.

Their research focused on a 5 MW solar plant in Kumasi using a dataset spanning 2018 to 2022 and found that RF outperformed DNN in short-term forecasts due to its lower computational requirements while DNN excelled in long-term trends by capturing seasonal patterns (Asiedu et al., 2024). The study also noted that data preprocessing such as handling missing values through interpolation was critical to achieving high accuracy. Recent Ghana-specific advances include (Alhassan et al. 2025), which evaluated single and hybrid machine learning models including XGBoost, Random Forest and ANN for in-situ PV generation forecasting at the 50 MWp Bui Solar Power Station. The hybrids (XGBoost-ANN and RF-XGBoost) demonstrated superior performance in multi-horizon predictions (day-ahead to month-ahead), with stacked ensembles reducing errors compared to single models (Alhassan et al. 2025).

These studies highlight the prospect of machine learning to enhance forecasting accuracy in regions with high solar potential but variable weather patterns.

2.4 Policy Frameworks for Renewable Energy Adoption and Integration

Effective integration of solar energy requires a flexible and robust policy framework that aligns with national energy goals. Policies such as feed-in-tariffs, tax incentives and renewable portfolio standards have driven solar adoption (REN21, 2020). For instance, feed-in tariffs have guaranteed fixed payments for solar energy producers encouraging investment in countries like Spain and Japan where solar capacity grew by 30% annually from 2010 to 2018 (International Renewable Energy Agency, 2015).

Renewable portfolio standards which mandates a percentage of energy from renewables have been adopted in over 100 countries and this contributing to a global renewable energy share of 26% by 2020 (International Renewable Energy Agency, 2015).

In Germany, aggressive policy support led to a significant 50% leap in solar energy adoption and overall capacity between 2010 and 2015 (Wirth, 2015). Germany's success was driven by the combined subsidies, low-interest loans and grid priority for renewables resulting in solar energy contributing 8.7% to the national electricity mix by 2015 (Wirth, 2015). The policy also supported decentralized solar installations with over 1.5 million rooftop systems installed by 2015 (Wirth, 2015).

In Africa, Kenya's remarkable renewable energy policy which comprise subsidies for off-grid solar systems has increased rural electrification rates by 20% since 2015 (International Renewable Energy Agency, 2015). Kenya's Solar Home Systems program supported by the World Bank provided affordable solar kits to over 1 million rural households (International Energy Agency, 2019). This resulted in reducing kerosene use and improving health outcomes (International Energy Agency, 2020). This model could inform Ghana's efforts to expand solar access in areas like the Northern and Upper West regions.

However, in Ghana, the Renewable Energy Act of 2011 aimed to achieve 10% renewable energy in the national mix by 2020, a target that was not fully met due to implementation challenges (Energy Commission Ghana, 2021). These challenges included inadequate funding, limited technical expertise resulting in only 2.8% renewable energy penetration by 2020 (Energy Commission Ghana, 2021). The Act's focus on large-scale projects such as the 20 MW Nzema Solar Plant overlooked smaller community-based systems that could address rural energy needs.

(Gyamfi, Modjinou and Djordjevic, 2015) argue that Ghana's policy framework lacks data-driven tools to guide solar investment. This has led to inefficient resource management and allocation.

Their analysis revealed that Ghana's energy sector allocated only 5% of its budget to renewables between 2010 and 2015. This was in a sharp contrast to 60% for thermal power which highlighted a misalignment with sustainability goals (Gyamfi, Modjinou and Djordjevic, 2015).

Another study by (Adenle, 2020) in Nigeria highlighted similar issues, noting that the absence of integrated forecasting models limits policy effectiveness. The findings from the various studies indicate the need for evidence-based policy recommendations supported by accurate forecasting tools.

2.5 Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

This study is grounded in Energy Transition Theory, which explains the gradual structural shift from fossil fuel-dominated energy systems to sustainable energy sources. The theory emphasizes technological innovation, policy alignment and institutional adaptation as critical drivers of transformation. In the Ghanaian context, the heavy reliance on thermal energy sources highlights the urgency of accelerating the transition toward renewable energy systems (Energy Commission Ghana, 2021).

Additionally, the study aligns with Rogers' Diffusion of Innovation Theory which explains how technological innovations are adopted within systems over time. Machine learning-based solar forecasting represents an innovation capable of influencing policy formulation, infrastructure planning and investment prioritization in Ghana's energy sector.

Conceptual framework of the research integrates three core components:

1. Acquisition of solar irradiance data

2. Machine learning-based forecasting and
3. Policy integration mechanisms.

The interaction between these components forms a data-driven decision-support system designed to enhance renewable energy planning (REN21, 2020).

Consequently, by embedding forecasting outputs within national policy strategies, the study operationalizes a transition pathway from reactive energy management to proactive, predictive and sustainability-oriented planning.

2.6 Gaps in Existing Literature

Evidence shows application of machine learning in other countries has advanced but in Ghana it is however limited. Most of the relevant literature focus on localized regions, for example, Kumasi, Northern Region rather than countrywide analyses restricting their utility for national planning (Asiedu et al., 2024). For instance, (Quansah et al., 2022) analyzed solar irradiance in only five of Ghana's 16 regions which limits the applicability of their findings for national energy strategies. Similarly, (Asiedu et al., 2024) focused exclusively on Kumasi neglecting regional variations in irradiance patterns across Ghana's diverse climatic zones such as the savanna and coastal regions

Additionally, there is a lack of integration between forecasting models and policy frameworks which has hindered strategic investment in solar infrastructure (Gyamfi, Modjinou and Djordjevic, 2015). This disconnect is evident in the absence of policy frameworks that leverage forecasting data to prioritize solar investments in high-irradiance regions like the Upper East, where irradiance exceeds 5.8 kWh/m²/day (Quansah et al., 2022). Furthermore, existing studies rarely address the economic feasibility of scaling up solar projects leaving policymakers without clear guidance on

cost-benefit analyses (Gyamfi, Modjinou and Djordjevic, 2015). This study intends to address these gaps by developing a comprehensive and countrywide machine learning-based forecasting model that integrates with policy frameworks to optimize renewable energy investment across all 16 regions in Ghana.

CHAPTER 3:

METHODOLOGY

3.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter outlines the methodology for developing a machine learning-based solar irradiance forecasting model. The methodology will cover data gathering, preprocessing, model development, evaluation and insights will drive policy analysis. A systematic and rigorous process will ensure robust results incorporating global best practices tailored to Ghana's tropical climate (Voyant *et al.*, 2017).

3.2 Research Design

3.2.1 Research Approach

The study will adopt a quantitative, experimental research approach. Historical solar irradiance data and machine learning techniques will be used to forecast solar potential across Ghana.

Multiple machine learning models will be compared to identify the most effective forecasting method for Ghana's tropical climate.

A policy analysis component will translate forecasting results into actionable recommendations. Statistical and computational methods will be applied to analyze numerical data to predict non-linear irradiance patterns with precision. The experimental design will test model performance under controlled conditions using metrics such as Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) (Sharma and Kakkar, 2018). This dual approach will aim to address Ghana's energy deficit which causes outages costing 2% to 6% of the GDP annually.

3.2.2 Research Framework

The research framework will combine data-driven modeling with policy evaluation. The process will begin with data collection from NASA's POWER dataset followed by preprocessing to ensure data quality. Machine learning models will be trained and validated to predict irradiance patterns. Results will inform policy recommendations for solar energy deployment, integration and strategic decision making. The framework will be iterative with feedback loops between model evaluation and policy formulation. This study will draw on global solar forecasting standards to achieve acceptable forecast accuracy above 80% as seen in similar studies (Voyant *et al.*, 2017). The approach will ensure scalability enabling adaptation to other African contexts (REN21, 2020)

3.3 Data Collection

3.3.1 Data Sources

Data will be sourced from the NASA POWER database and the Ghana Meteorological Agency (GMet) for the period 1984 to 2020. These sources will provide Global Horizontal Irradiance (GHI), Direct Normal Irradiance (DNI), Diffuse Horizontal Irradiance (DHI), temperature, humidity, cloud cover and wind speed. The NASA POWER database will supply satellite-derived data at $0.5^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$ resolution which has been validated for tropical regions with an accuracy of $\pm 10 \text{ W/m}^2$ (Quansah *et al.*, 2022). GMet datasets will provide ground-based measurements from 22 weather stations across Ghana ensuring local precision. These sources will capture Ghana's solar potential which averages $4.5 \text{ kWh/m}^2/\text{day}$ to $6.0 \text{ kWh/m}^2/\text{day}$ critical for forecasting (Voyant *et al.*, 2017). Additional variables like cloud cover ranging from 0-100% and wind speed ranging from 0-15 m/s will enhance model robustness (Wright *et al.* 2018). Although GMet data were initially considered to enhance ground-based precision, access limitations and incomplete

temporal coverage across all regions restricted its integration into final modelling process. As a result, NASA POWER data were prioritized due to a continuous coverage, standardized resolution and suitability for national scale analysis. Consequently, this will lead to methodological consistency of data across all regions in Ghana.

3.3.2 Data Characteristics

The dataset includes monthly Global Horizontal Irradiance averages (W/m^2) for Ghana over 40 years capturing climate change variations. The spatial resolution of $0.5^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$ will account for regional differences. This resolution also captures variations such as higher GHI in the savanna north with irradiance projections around $5.8\text{kWh}/\text{m}^2/\text{day}$ to $6.0\text{kWh}/\text{m}^2/\text{day}$ versus coastal south $4.5\text{kWh}/\text{m}^2/\text{day}$ to $5.0\text{kWh}/\text{m}^2/\text{day}$ respectively (Quansah et al., 2022). The dataset will include meteorological variables to account for seasonal effects like harmattan dust reducing irradiance by up to 15% (Wright et al. 2018). Temporal granularity ensures accurate trend analysis, supporting policy decisions (Ozoegwu, Mgbemene and Ozor, 2017).

3.4 Data Preprocessing

Preprocessing will ensure data quality through the following steps:

1. Cleaning: Linear interpolation will be used to impute missing values to maintain temporal continuity (Voyant *et al.*, 2017).
2. Normalization: GHI and meteorological variables will be scaled to $[0,1]$ for model convergence (Sharma and Kakkar, 2018).
3. Feature Engineering: Temporal month, season and spatial latitude, longitude features will capture regional and seasonal patterns (Ozoegwu, Mgbemene and Ozor, 2017).

4. **Outlier Detection:** Z-score analysis will remove outliers exceeding three standard deviations (Castle and Hendry, 2024). Cleaning of datasets will address data gaps affecting 2% to 5% of GMet records due to sensor failures. Interpolation will reduce errors by 5% to 10% as demonstrated in similar studies (Voyant *et al.*, 2017). Normalization will use min-max scaling to stabilize gradient-based models like DNN. Feature engineering will include dummy variables for wet seasons that is, April to October and dry season November to March seasons thereby improving accuracy by 15% as observed in similar studies (Ozoegwu, Mgbemene and Ozor, 2017). Outlier detection will mitigate anomalies from cloud cover spikes and dust ensuring data integrity (Castle and Hendry, 2024).

3.5 Machine Learning Models

Machine learning techniques will be employed to model complex patterns in historical irradiance data that are difficult to model using traditional statistical approaches. Given the availability of labelled irradiance observations from NASA's power dataset, this study will adopt supervised machine learning methods to learn relationships between the data.

Supervised learning is specifically suitable for this study as it enables predictive modelling based on known target variable (Voyant *et al.*, 2017). The approach allows for quantitative evaluation of model performance with future predictions.

Figure 3.1 Machine-learning model structure

The Figure 3.1 demonstrates the step-by-step process for building a machine learning model. The process will involve three mainly stages:

1. Data acquisition and preprocessing: Collecting, cleaning and transforming raw data
2. Model development and training: This will involve application of algorithms such regression, ensemble methods and deep learning to capture patterns from the data.
3. Evaluation and deployment: Assessment of the models will be done through statistical metrics such as Mean Absolute Error and Root Mean Square Error to validate the models.

Insights derived will be used to provide recommendations for policymakers and stakeholders to integrate into national energy policy frameworks.

End-to-End Machine Learning Workflow

Figure 3.2 End-to-end machine learning model

The Figure 3.3 demonstrates the steps used to build machine learning models. Machine learning models involve the data aggregation and processing stage, algorithm selection, model training, testing and validation and persistence.

Three models were selected for solar forecasting:

1. Random Forests (RF): An ensemble method effective for non-linear data (Castle and Hendry, 2024).
2. XGBoost: A gradient boosting algorithm with high accuracy for non-linear data (Sharma and Kakkar, 2018).

3. Deep Neural Networks (DNN): A deep learning model for complex temporal patterns (Voyant *et al.*, 2017).

RF will use 100 to 500 trees to handle high-dimensional data reducing overfitting in Ghana's variable climate. XGBoost employs gradient boosting with learning rates of 0.01 to 0.3 achieving 10% to 20% higher accuracy than traditional (Sharma and Kakkar, 2018). DNNs will apply 2 to 5 hidden layers with Rectilinear Linear Activation (ReLU) capturing seasonal trends with potential to achieve an R^2 of up to 0.85 in similar studies (Voyant *et al.*, 2017). Models will be implemented using python programming language leveraging existing machine learning libraries including scikit-learn, XGBoost and TensorFlow. These frameworks provide robust and well-validated implementations of machine learning, deep learning algorithms that enables reproducible model development, training and evaluation.

Regression Models for Solar Forecasting

Figure 3.3 Model Design for Solar Forecasting

Figure 3.3 delves deep into the algorithms that will be adopted to build the XGBoost, DNN and Random Forest learning models.

3.5.1 Model Training

The dataset will be split into 80% training and 20% testing sets. A 5-fold cross-validation approach will prevent overfitting (Ozoegwu, Mgbemene and Ozor, 2017).

Figure 3.4 Validation of machine learning models

The Figure 3.4 demonstrates training and testing phase of machine learning models. Data can be split into smaller chunks to enable machine learning algorithms to model patterns in data efficiently.

Grid search will optimize hyperparameters to minimize MAE and RMSE (Sharma and Kakkar, 2018). Cross-validation will reduce variance by 10% thereby enhancing model reliability

(Ozoegwu, Mgbemene and Ozor, 2017). For Random Forest models, the number of trees will be evaluated at 100, 200 and 500. XGBoost models will be tuned using learning rates of 0.01, 0.1 and 0.3 while Deep Learning models will be tested with 2 to 5 hidden layers and 64 to 256 neurons per layer. Training will use a batch size of 32 and 100 epochs for DNNs with early stoppage to prevent overfitting (Voyant *et al.*, 2017).

3.5.2 Model Evaluation

Model performance will be evaluated using a combination of statistical error and fitting metrics to assess predictive accuracy and suitability for energy planning in Ghana's context.

The following metrics will be used:

1. Mean Absolute Error (MAE): Measures average prediction error in W/m^2 targeting errors below $20 W/m^2$ for energy planning and it is considered reliable for solar energy planning (Wright *et al.* 2018).
2. Root Mean Square Error (RMSE): Highlight larger prediction errors which is critical for assessing model performance under harmattan-related data and extreme climatic conditions (Quansah *et al.*, 2022).
3. Coefficient of Determination (R^2): Indicates variance explained by the model aiming for values above 0.85 regarded as strong predictive performance in line with prior studies (Castle and Hendry, 2024). Evaluation will include per-region analysis to identify model performance variations, with northern regions expected to show lower errors due to higher GHI stability (Quansah *et al.*, 2022)

3.6 Analysis

Policy recommendations will be developed based on forecasting results to identify high-potential months and regions. The analysis will use frameworks from (REN21, 2020) and (Gyamfi, Modjinou and Djordjevic, 2015) focusing on:

1. Investment Prioritization: Targeting regions like Northern and Upper East with high GHI above 5.8 kWh/m²/day for solar farms (Quansah et al., 2022). Hybrid Energy Strategies: Combining solar and hydropower for seasonal balance potentially reducing thermal reliance by 30% (Gyamfi, Modjinou and Djordjevic, 2015).
2. Incentive Structures: Proposing feed-in tariffs and tax breaks to increase solar capacity by 20% by 2030 modeled on Germany's tariffs (Wirth, 2015). Recommendations will be validated with stakeholder consultations, including Ghana's Energy Commission through evidence-based approach from the research.

3.7 Ethical Considerations

This study will adhere to established research ethics principles including transparency, academic integrity and responsible data usage. All datasets utilized are publicly available and properly cited. Forecasting outputs will be presented objectively with acknowledgement of uncertainty margins to avoid overstatement of predictive capability.

To address potential algorithmic bias, model performance will be evaluated across latitudinal zones (northern savanna vs. southern coastal) to ensure equitable representation of regional

climatic variations. This mitigates risks of forecasts disproportionately favoring data-rich northern areas, which could exacerbate regional energy inequities.

Moreover, policy recommendations will be developed cautiously to avoid misinterpretation that could lead to inequitable regional investment decisions. Emphasis will be placed on ensuring that solar infrastructure prioritization does not marginalize southern regions but rather support balanced national energy development.

Summarily, the study will adhere to research ethics by:

1. Using publicly available datasets with proper attribution.
2. Ensuring transparency and reproducibility of modeling approaches.
3. Avoiding data manipulation or misrepresentation of results.

3.8 Limitations

1. **Data Resolution:** The $0.5^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$ resolution may miss microclimatic (Quansah et al., 2022).
2. **Computational Constraints:** Limited computing resources may restrict DNN complexity (Castle and Hendry, 2024). Mitigation will include adoption of computing cloud environments to resolve the computational resource inadequacy.

CHAPTER 4:

RESULTS

4.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter presents the empirical findings derived from the application of the methodology.

The results are organized to align with the specific objectives of the study. The chapter commences with a detailed description of the preprocessed solar irradiance dataset. An exposition of the spatial patterns of solar irradiance across Ghana closely follows. The performance metrics of the three machine learning models that is, Random Forest (RF), XGBoost and Deep Neural Networks (DNN) are delineated. The models will be quantitatively evaluated using Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and coefficient of determination values.

The chapter further digs into the forecasting outcomes identifying regions with the highest solar energy potential based on predicted irradiance trends. Visual representations such as heatmaps and predictive plots are integrated to facilitate analysis of the insights. All results are reported objectively without interpretive analysis to maintain the integrity of the empirical evidence. The findings are grounded in the historical dataset spanning 1984 to 2022 sourced from the NASA POWER database, a global dataset providing climate and solar resource data for energy modelling. The datasets encompass variables such as Global Horizontal Irradiance (GHI), Direct Normal Irradiance (DNI), Diffuse Horizontal Irradiance (DHI), temperature, humidity, cloud cover and wind speed. Descriptive statistics and visualizations are employed to encapsulate the dataset's characteristics ensuring a robust foundation for the subsequent model evaluations and forecasts.

4.2 Descriptive Analysis of Solar Irradiance Data

The preprocessed dataset comprises monthly averages of solar irradiance metrics across Ghana aggregated from a total of 19,200 data points of 40 years by 12 months and by 40 grid points approximating regional coverage at $0.5^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$ resolution. The primary variable of interest was Global Horizontal Irradiance (GHI) and it exhibited a national annual mean of 5.12 kWh/m²/day. GHI also exhibited standard deviation of 0.78 kWh/m²/day indicating moderate variability influenced by seasonal and regional factors. The minimum recorded GHI was 3.45 kWh/m²/day which was observed in the Greater Accra Region during the peak wet season month of June. However, the maximum GHI reached 6.45 kWh/m²/day in the Upper East Region during the dry season month of February. Direct Normal Irradiance (DNI) averaged 4.85 kWh/m²/day nationally. However, with values in northern savanna regions achieving mean of 5.42 kWh/m²/day compared to southern coastal areas with mean of 4.28 kWh/m²/day reflected the impact of latitude and atmospheric conditions.

Figure 4.1 Seasonal GHI comparison

The Figure 4.1 bar chart provides a concise dry season against wet season comparison by aggregating the dry season phase from November to March against the wet season phase from April to October. The chart proves Ghana’s solar resource reliability with wet season remaining visibly viable for PV systems while dry season approaches Class 1 solar resource status globally. This communicates investment-grade seasonal persistence to stakeholders.

Diffuse Horizontal Irradiance (DHI) showed a mean of 2.15 kWh/m²/day with elevated levels during wet seasons due to increased cloud scattering. Ancillary meteorological variables included temperature with national mean of 27.8°C and range from 22.5 to 33. 2°C. The recorded humidity had a mean of 78%, ranging from 45% to 95% whereas cloud cover achieved

a mean of 52% ranging from 10% to 90% and wind speed achieved a mean of 3.2 m/s ranging from 0.5m/s to 8.5 m/s. These variables were normalized to a [0,1] scale post-cleaning where linear interpolation addressed 3.2% missing values and Z-score-based outlier removal eliminated 1.8% of anomalous entries exceeding three standard deviations as demonstrated in similar studies in France (Wright et al. 2018)

Spatial distribution analysis revealed pronounced latitudinal gradients with northern regions, Upper East, Upper West and Northern consistently demonstrating higher irradiance levels compared to southern regional counterparts like Greater Accra, Central and Western. For instance, the Upper East Region recorded an annual GHI mean of 5.85 kWh/m²/day, whereas the Greater Accra Region averaged 4.62 kWh/m²/day. Temporal patterns emphasized seasonal variations: dry season months of November to March yielded a mean GHI of 5.68 kWh/m²/day while wet season months April to October averaged 4.56 kWh/m²/day. This is attributable to increased cloud cover and precipitation during the latter period.

Figure 4.2 Regional Irradiance Heatmap

The heatmap in Figure 4.2 illustrates the overall spatial distribution of mean annual solar irradiance in kWh/m²/day across Ghana's latitudes and longitudes with warmer colors yellow to red indicating higher irradiance values.

Figure 4.3 Regional Labeled Heatmap

The heatmap in Figure 4.3 depicts solar irradiance across Ghana with non-overlapping labels for the 16 regions. The heatmap is divided by a dashed line at approximately 8°N to distinguish southern and northern zones facilitating identification of regional variations.

Figure 4.4 Seasonal Heatmap for Months

The heatmap in Figure 4.4 presents mean irradiance by dry and wet seasons and months from January to December. The annotated values in each cell represents average GHI in kWh/m²/day highlighting temporal fluctuations.

The visualizations corroborate the descriptive statistics emphasizing the northern regions' superior solar potential and the dry season's elevated irradiance.

4.3 Machine Learning Model Performance

The three machine learning models were trained on 80% of the dataset and evaluated on the remaining 20% using a 5-fold cross-validation strategy to mitigate overfitting. Hyperparameters were optimized via grid search: for Random Forest, the number of trees ranged from 100 to 500;

for XGBoost, learning rates varied from 0.01 to 0.3 with maximum depths of 3 to 6; for DNN, layer configurations included 2 to 5 hidden layers with 64 neurons to 256 neurons per layer, trained over 100 epochs with a batch size of 32 and early stopping. Feature inputs comprised latitude, longitude, year and a binary season indicator wet or dry. This enabled the models to capture spatio-temporal dynamics.

Table 4.1 Random Forest Model Performance on Test Set

Metric	Value	Interpretation
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.112 kWh/m ² /day	On average, predictions deviated by 0.112 kWh/m ² /day from actual values.
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.1495 kWh/m ² /day	Typical prediction error magnitude is about 0.15 kWh/m ² /day.
R-squared (R ²)	0.9196	The model explains 91.96% of the variance in solar irradiance.

The Random Forest model achieved a Mean Absolute Error of 0.112 kWh/m²/day, Root Mean Square Error of 0.1495 kWh/m²/day and R-squared of 0.9196 on the test set. These metrics indicate that on average the model's predictions deviated by approximately 0.15 kWh/m²/day from actual value explaining 91.96% of the variance in solar irradiance.

Table 4.2 XGBoost Model Performance on Test Set

Metric	Value	Interpretation
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.085 kWh/m ² /day	On average, predictions deviated by 0.085 kWh/m ² /day from actual values.
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.1086 kWh/m ² /day	Typical prediction error magnitude is about 0.11 kWh/m ² /day.
R-squared (R ²)	0.9575	The model explains 95.75% of the variance in solar irradiance.

The XGBoost model recorded an MAE of 0.085 kWh/m²/day, RMSE of 0.1086 kWh/m²/day and R² of 0.9575 demonstrating superior precision with an average error of about 0.11 kWh/m²/day and accounting for 95.75% of the data's variance.

Table 4.3 Deep Neural Network Model Performance on Test Set

Metric	Value	Interpretation
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.328 kWh/m ² /day	On average, predictions deviated by 0.328 kWh/m ² /day from actual values.
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.4448 kWh/m ² /day	Typical prediction error magnitude is about 0.44 kWh/m ² /day.
R-squared (R ²)	0.2879	The model explains only 28.79% of the variance in solar irradiance.

The Deep Neural Network model yielded an MAE of 0.328 kWh/m²/day, RMSE of 0.4448 kWh/m²/day and coefficient of determination value of 0.2879 which reflects higher prediction errors averaging 0.44 kWh/m²/day and explaining only 28.79% of the variance.

Cross-validation confirmed consistency with RF showing a mean RMSE of 0.152 ± 0.012 , XGBoost 0.110 ± 0.008 and DNN 0.452 ± 0.035 across folds.

Figure 4.5 RF Predicted vs Actual Plot

The scatter plot in Figure 4.5 compares predicted versus actual solar irradiance values for the Random Forest model with a 45-degree reference line. It achieved an RMSE of 0.1495 and coefficient of determination value of 0.9196 indicating tight clustering around the line. This signified accurate predictions with minimal deviation.

Figure 4.6 XGBoost Predicted vs Actual Plot

The scatter plot in Figure 4.6 also illustrates predicted versus actual irradiance for XGBoost which aligned closely to the 45-degree line with RMSE of 0.1086 and coefficient of determination value of 0.9575 reflect the model's high fidelity in capturing data patterns.

Figure 4.7 DNN Predicted vs Actual Plot

The scatter plot in Figure 4.7 shows predicted versus actual values for the DNN with wider dispersion. The RMSE of 0.4448 and coefficient of determination value of 0.2879 highlight greater errors and lower explanatory power.

Figure 4.8 RF Feature Importance

The bar chart in Figure 4.8 ranks feature importance's for Random Forest model emphasizing latitude and month number as key predictors.

Figure 4.9 XGBoost Feature Importance

The bar chart in Figure 4.9 displays feature importance for XGBoost underscoring the dominance of seasonal and spatial variables.

The Figures visually substantiate the quantitative metrics illustrating model behaviors across the test dataset.

4.4 Forecasting Results and Identification of High-Potential Areas

Using the best-performing model that is, XGBoost, based on superior metrics, annual solar irradiance trends were forecasted for 2023 to 2030. With the projection, a national mean increase of 0.05 kWh/m²/day per year was observed and this aligned with historical warming patterns.

Regionally, the Upper East Region forecasted the highest annual GHI at 6.02 kWh/m²/day

followed by Upper West Region with 5.95 kWh/m²/day and Northern Region with 5.88 kWh/m²/day. Southern regions like Greater Accra projected lower values at 4.68 kWh/m²/day. Monthly forecasts identified February in the dry season as the peak month nationally with a mean of 5.92 kWh/m²/day. The northern regions had GHI exceeding 6.2 kWh/m²/day. Wet season lows occurred in the month of July with a mean of 4.32 kWh/m²/day particularly in coastal areas below 4.0 kWh/m²/day.

Table 4.4 XGBoost-Based Solar Irradiance Forecasts (2023–2030)

Category	Result	Details
National Trend	+0.05 kWh/m ² /day per year	Aligns with historical warming patterns.
Regional Highs	Upper East: 6.02 kWh/m ² /day Upper West: 5.95 kWh/m ² /day Northern: 5.88 kWh/m ² /day	Northern regions projected highest GHI.
Regional Lows	Greater Accra: 4.68 kWh/m ² /day	Southern or coastal regions project lower GHI.
Monthly Peak	February: 5.92 kWh/m ² /day	National peak; Northern regions exceed 6.2 kWh/m ² /day.
Monthly Low	July: 4.32 kWh/m ² /day	Wet season minimum; coastal areas drop below 4.0 kWh/m ² /day.

To account for predictive uncertainty, a ± 0.12 kWh/m²/day confidence interval was computed based on cross-validation residual variance. Forecast projections should therefore be interpreted within this range, acknowledging potential climatic variability and model sensitivity.

Incorporating uncertainty bounds enhances forecast reliability for policy-level planning (Sharma and Kakkar, 2018).

High-potential months included January to March and November to December across all regions with northern savanna zones consistently above 5.5 kWh/m²/day. Regions with optimal potential were Upper East with 8 months above 5.5 kWh/m²/day, Upper West with 7 months and Northern with 7 months. This contrasted with southern regions like Western with 5 months and Central with 4 months above 5.5 kWh/m²/day respectively.

Figure 4.10 Solar irradiation projection in Ghana

The Figure 4.10 supports the assertion that in the next years solar availability will continue to persist and the best months to invest remains the dry season in Ghana. The dry season’s Global Horizontal Irradiance consistently peaks above 5.0 kWh/m²/day.

The results provide a granular basis for strategic planning, with forecasts validated against 2020 to 2022 holdout data showing an RMSE of 0.115 kWh/m²/day. Integration of predictive models

into national energy planning backed by evidenced-based will ensure stakeholders take informed decisions.

CHAPTER 5:

DISCUSSION

5.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter interprets the results presented by contextualizing them within the broader theoretical and empirical landscape of solar energy forecasting and renewable energy policy in Ghana. The discussion delves into the implications of the descriptive data analysis, model performances and forecasting outcomes in relation to the study's objectives. It also draws comparisons with extant literature to highlight contributions and divergences. It explores the practical ramifications for Ghana's energy sector particularly in mitigating reliance on thermal power and hydropower vulnerabilities. It also helps in advancing alignment with Sustainable Development Goal 7. Ethical considerations, limitations and avenues for future research are examined to provide a holistic appraisal.

The study maintains evidence-based approach emphasizing the study's role in bridging gaps in countrywide, data-driven solar irradiance modeling. By integrating quantitative metrics with qualitative policy insights, the study emphasizes the transformative potential of machine learning in fostering a sustainable and resilient energy mix for Ghana. The study provides an evidence-based suggested recommendations amid escalating demands that have precipitated economic losses equivalent to 2% to 6% of GDP annually (Energy Commission Ghana, 2021).

5.2 Interpretation of Descriptive Results

The descriptive analysis of the solar irradiance dataset reveals a robust foundation for forecasting with national GHI means of 5.12 kWh/m²/day aligning closely with prior estimates of 4.5 kWh/m²/day to 6.0 kWh/m²/day (Quansah et al., 2022). This affirmed Ghana's substantial solar potential. The observed latitudinal gradient wherein northern regions exhibit 20% to 30% higher irradiance than southern ones can be attributed to reduced cloud cover and proximity to the equator's savanna belt.

Figure 5.1 Cloud cover for Ghana from 1984-2022

The Figure 5.1 shows a critical validation of chart plots of Direct Horizontal Irradiance against Global Horizontal Irradiance where higher values indicate greater cloud scattering. The relationship emphasizes that high humidity during the wet season suppresses Global Horizontal Irradiance. However, on the contrary, Harmattan dust minimally impacts solar irradiance. Temporal variations with dry seasons yielding 24% higher GHI than wet seasons emphasizes the influence of meteorological factors like humidity and precipitation mirroring patterns in analogous tropical climates such as Nigeria (Ozoegwu, Mgbemene and Ozor, 2017).

Figure 5.2 Monthly solar irradiance breakdown for Ghana

The Figure 5.2 displays Ghana’s monthly average Global Horizontal Irradiance across all latitudes and longitudes from NASA Power data from 1984 to 2022 and it is measured in kWh/m²/day. The gold shading highlights the dry season which starts from November to March where the GHI consistently higher than for the wet season periods. This demonstrates GHI is generally in the dry season than it is for the wet season in Ghana.

The integration of ancillary variables such as temperature, humidity, cloud cover and wind speed enhanced data richness. This enabled the models to account for up to 15% efficiency reductions from dust and clouds as noted in South African contexts (Wright et al. 2018). These findings

validate the preprocessing steps where interpolation and normalization mitigated data gaps and scaled variables effectively. Overall, the results substantiate the geographical advantage. This positioned northern regions as suitable locations for solar infrastructure and dry months as optimal for photovoltaic deployment thereby addressing the problem statement's call for data-driven frameworks to counter thermal dependency. The trend also achieved an aberration where the months immediately after the dry season or before the wet season achieved significant solar irradiance values. This indicates that investment in solar infrastructure can also be possible in those months thereby improving coverage.

Figure 5.3 Solar irradiance Distribution by month in Ghana

The Figure 5.3 demonstrates consistently higher solar irradiance values for dry seasons months of November to March.

5.3 Interpretation Of Machine Learning Model Performance

The comparative evaluation of the machine learning models elucidates distinct strengths and limitations with XGBoost emerging as the superior performer with RMSE with 0.1086 kWh/m²/day and coefficient of determination of 0.9575. The metrics of XGBoost model outperformed Random Forest with RMSE of 0.1495 and coefficient of determination of 0.9196 and markedly surpassed DNN with a RMSE of 0.4448 and coefficient of determination of 0.2879. XGBoost gradient boosting mechanism which iteratively corrects errors through tree ensembles adeptly captured non-linear spatio-temporal relationships in the dataset achieving 95.75% variance explanation. This feat aligns with (Sharma and Kakkar, 2018)'s findings of Gradient Boosting Model (GBM)'s 10% error reduction in humid Indian climates similar to Ghana's. The low RMSE indicates precise predictions with average errors constituting less than 2% of mean GHI. This rendered it suitable for strategic energy planning where accuracy is paramount. Random Forest's solid performance explaining 91.96% of variance stems from its bagging approach that reduces overfitting in high-dimensional (Voyant *et al.*, 2017). Although its slightly higher RMSE suggests minor limitations in handling extreme seasonal outliers like Harmattan dust events.

Conversely, the DNN's suboptimal metrics reflect challenges in converging on complex temporal patterns with the available dataset size and computational constraints, as (Voyant *et al.*, 2017) noted ANN's sensitivity to training data volume. The low coefficient of determination value of 0.2879 implies it captured only basic trends potentially due to insufficient epochs or unscaled features despite normalization efforts.

Feature importance analyses highlight latitude and month number as dominant predictors emphasizing geographical and seasonal drivers over year or longitude. This informs model refinement through variables prioritization. The predicted versus actual plots visually affirm these metrics: XGBoost tight clustering along the 45-degree line demonstrates high fidelity while DNN's dispersion highlights prediction scatter. These interpretations address research question 3 by identifying XGBoost as the most effective under Ghanaian conditions and extend literature by providing a countrywide benchmark against localized studies (Quansah *et al.*, 2022). Thus, the study enhances forecasting precision for national-scale applications.

XGBoost's superior performance over Random Forest in this study can be attributed to its gradient boosting framework. XGBoost sequentially constructs decision trees to minimize residuals from prior iterations which enables more precise capturing of complex non-linear interactions and seasonal outliers prevalent in Ghana's tropical climate. Unlike Random Forest's parallel bagging approach which averages predictions to reduce variance but may smooth over sharp temporal gradients (Quansah *et al.*, 2022). In contrast, XGBoost incorporates shrinkage and regularization (L1/L2 penalties) to prevent overfitting while maintaining sensitivity to extreme meteorological variations. This advantage is consistent with findings in similar tropical and meteorological forecasting contexts, where XGBoost frequently achieves 20-30% lower RMSE than RF on non-stationary time-series data due to its ability to prioritize difficult-to-

predict instances during training (Asiedu et al., 2024). In contrast, the DNN's poorer convergence stems from the relatively modest dataset size and limited computational epochs which hindered its ability to learn deep temporal patterns effectively.

5.4 Interpretation of Forecasting Results and High-Potential Identification

The XGBoost-derived forecasts project a modest upward trend in irradiance of 0.05 kWh/m²/day per year which is attributable to climate-induced warming that may intensify solar availability. This aligned with (REN21, 2020) projections for tropical regions. Regionally, the Upper East, Upper West and Northern regions' elevated forecasts which are above 5.88 kWh/m²/day corroborates the findings of (Quansah et al., 2022) who emphasized the northern savanna solar superiority driven by lower humidity and extended dry periods. This insight positioned the northern regions' as high-potential hubs for large-scale solar farms. Monthly peaks in February and dry season dominance reflect reduced atmospheric interference enabling optimized photovoltaic output during these periods. As opposed to wet season dips in July which necessitate hybrid strategies with hydropower. The identification of seven to eight high-potential months in northern regions versus four to five in southern ones addresses research question 2 which offers granular insights absent in prior localized studies like (Asiedu et al., 2024). The heatmaps visually reinforce these patterns with northern zones in red hues signifying investment viability. These results directly tackle the problem statement's gap in dynamic tools for resource allocation which demonstrates how forecasts can guide infrastructure prioritization. This can

help in potentially reducing thermal fuel imports by 30% to 40% through targeted solar integration and fostering resilience against hydropower variability (Energy Commission Ghana, 2021).

5.5 Implications for Policy and Renewable Energy Integration

The findings highlight the strategic importance of Northern Region as a potential solar hub which demonstrates that spatial and seasonal variations in irradiance can inform evidence-based energy planning. The results emphasize the need for continuous integration of meteorological forecasts into national energy modelling to improve grid reliability and long-term planning. Moreover, aligning the insights with SDG 7 strengthens the case for sustainable electrification pathways that reduce dependence on thermal generation while promoting regional equity in access to renewable resource.

Figure 5.4 Solar Irradiance Levels For Months

The Figure 5.4 shows that Northern Regions consistently had higher solar irradiance values in the dry season. Seasonal progression flows from left to right with wet season coastal cloud bias and consistently higher Global Horizontal Irradiance for the reddish cells during the dry season. The yellow or red colormap intuitively maps higher Global Horizontal Irradiance as hotter colors which may guide utility project siting. Implementation barriers include northern grid infrastructure gaps with over \$500 million upgrade cost (World Bank, 2021).

Overall, these implications bridge the literature gap by linking machine learning forecasts to policy which enhances sustainability and energy security.

5.6 Recommendations

From the research and based on the findings it is recommended that a short-term and long-term approach should be adopted in order for Ghana to have a resilient energy mix.

Short-Term Policy Recommendations (1-3 years)

1. Feed-in tariffs and tax incentives as already outlined in Ghana's Renewable Energy policy should be implemented and adjusted seasonally to reflect solar availability patterns.
2. Forecast integration tools should be adopted in national energy planning to enhance grid stability and a shift towards cleaner energy. Integration of forecasts into national planning could optimize grid stability and rural electrification, emulating Kenya's 20% rural boost (REN21, 2020). This aligns with Sustainable Development Goal number 7 by promoting clean energy through evidence-based strategies that mitigate financial burdens on energy infrastructure.
3. Prioritization of pilot solar farms in the northern regions should be carried out.

Long-Term Policy Recommendations (3-10 years)

1. A comprehensive review and amendment of Renewable Energy Act to formally incorporate data-driven investment frameworks should be carried out.
2. Development of a hybrid solar-hydro energy balancing strategy should be adopted to stabilize seasonal energy supply fluctuations.

CHAPTER 6:

CONCLUSION

6.1 Introduction

This study advances Ghana's renewable energy agenda through precise machine learning-driven solar forecasting. The northern regions and dry months were identified as optimal for investment and proffering policy pathways for integration. By outperforming benchmarks with XGBoost's metrics, the study fills critical gaps in countrywide analyses thereby paving the way for a sustainable and diversified energy mix. This helps in alleviating thermal burdens and aligns with global sustainability imperatives.

The study also contributes to the discourse on sustainable energy development in Ghana by leveraging machine learning-driven solar irradiance forecasting to inform strategic energy planning. Through rigorous application of Random Forest, XGBoost and Deep Neural Network models the study has clarified the spatio-temporal dynamics of solar potential across Ghana. XGBoost emerged as the most robust predictor by achieving a Root Mean Square Error of 0.1086 kWh/m²/day and a coefficient of determination value of 0.9575. These metrics emphasized the model's precision in capturing complex patterns within the datasets for solar irradiance from the NASA Power dataset spanning 1984 to 2022. The northern regions particularly Upper East, Upper West and Northern Region were identified as high-potential zones with annual Global Horizontal Irradiance exceeding 5.88 kWh/m²/day. Alongside the delineation of dry season months as optimal for photovoltaic deployment, the study also provides an evidence-based foundation for infrastructure prioritization. These findings address critical gaps in countrywide solar resource assessments offering dynamic recommendations to mitigate

Ghana's reliance on thermal and hydropower sources. These sources have historically precipitated economic losses of 2% to 6% of GDP annually (Energy Commission Ghana, 2021). The study's forecasting outcomes by projecting a modest irradiance increase of 0.05 kWh/m²/day per year align with global climate trends and reinforce the viability of northern savanna zones for large-scale solar investments. By integrating these insights with policy recommendations, such as feed-in tariffs and tax incentives modeled on successful frameworks like Germany's Energiewende (Wirth, 2015). This research advocates for a transformative shift towards a diversified and resilient energy mix. The approach not only supports Ghana's Renewable Energy Act (2011) ambitions but also aligns with Sustainable Development Goal number 7 by promoting affordable and clean energy access (Obeng-Darko, 2019). Ethical considerations which include equitable resource allocation and data integrity further enhance the study's applicability to national energy strategies.

Despite its contributions, the study acknowledges limitations such as the 0.5° resolution's potential oversight of microclimatic variations and computational constraints on Deep Neural Network performance. Future research should explore higher-resolution data, hybrid machine learning ensembles and real-time sensor integrations to enhance forecasting accuracy.

Additionally, incorporating economic cost-benefit analyses and stakeholder simulations could bridge implementation gap by further aligning with policy imperatives. While Germany's Energiewende (Wirth, 2015) provides a tariff model, Ghana's lower fiscal capacity requires adaptation such as phased, donor-supported subsidies rather full guarantees.

In conclusion, this study establishes a data-driven paradigm for enhancing Ghana's energy sector sustainability by providing actionable insights for policymakers and stakeholders. This

perpetuates the nation's commitment to fostering a clean, equitable and economically viable energy future.

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